

Development of Busy Book Learning Media Based on the Universe Theme to Develop English Vocabulary for Early Childhood of Kindergarten Group B At TK Amir Hamzah Medan

Siti Nur Raliza^{1*}, Suri Handayani Damanik²
State University of Medan

Corresponding Author: Siti Nur Raliza sitinurralija@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Busy Book Learning Media, English Vocabulary, Early Childhood Education

Received: 02, August

Revised: 12, September

Accepted: 22, October

©2023 Raliza, Damanik: This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Atribusi 4.0 Internasional](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

This research was carried out to determine the feasibility and practicality of busy book learning media based on the theme of the universe in developing the English vocabulary of early childhood in Kindergarten Group B. The research is R&D research using the ADDIE model (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation). Based on the research results, a score of 3.875 was obtained from media experts in the "Very Feasible" category. From media experts, a score of 2.9 was obtained in the "Decent" category in the first stage and a score of 3.8 was obtained in the "Very Feasible" category in the second stage. From the practicality test, a score of 3.7 was obtained in the "Very Feasible" category.

INTRODUCTION

All Indonesian people are allowed to obtain education by the state. There is no exception for children from early childhood to adulthood or old age who have the right to receive education. The reason why young children also have the right to get this opportunity is because young children are in their golden age. The golden period or in other words the Golden Age is a period that occurs between the ages of 0-6 years, where children experience rapid growth and development, so they need to receive attention and stimulation so that they can grow and develop optimally. Maria Montessori (in Paramita, 2019) stated that "The most important period of life is not the age of university studies, but the first one, the period from birth to the age of six". The most important periods in a child's life lie from the beginning of birth to the age of 6 years.

These developmental aspects are important to develop in early childhood, including language development. Language development must be stimulated from an early age so that children have insight and literacy skills. Children's literacy abilities will influence their daily lives because language is a tool for communication that connects one human being with another human being. In Indonesia, language teaching and learning activities use Indonesian and foreign languages. One of these foreign languages is English, which is also the first foreign language in Indonesia. English has become a world language for various fields, including military, economics, politics, health, technology, and even education (Izzan and Mahfuddin, 2007).

In terms of education, English needs to be introduced and taught to children from an early age. Children gain many benefits from learning English. Children who receive foreign language introduction treatment from an early age have advantages in terms of intellectual flexibility, academic skills, language, and social skills (Mustafa in Khairani, 2016). Apart from that, introducing English to children as the nation's next generation can also be a provision to face obstacles in the future so that there are quality human resources that can compete globally. Based on the results of pre-observations and interviews with Mrs. Rini, Kindergarten B Class Teacher, at TK Amir Hamzah Medan, it is known that the use of English has not been carried out optimally because the teacher is still focused on prioritizing the material left behind during the Covid-19 pandemic. The teacher only uses the habituation method in simple expressions, such as when asking for permission to go to the bathroom, or when singing before entering class.

However, this habituation was not carried out consistently, so the child did not say the expression when necessary, and when the teacher reminded him of the expression the child seemed to be stuttering, and could not even say it. In class learning, the teacher inserts a color guessing activity in English, but this activity is not carried out by the theme being taught. This happens because of the teacher's lack of English language skills and the absence of learning media to introduce English. Children's mastery of

English vocabulary does not develop because of this. Mrs. Rini also said that the Group B students at TK Amir Hamzah Medan were very interested in visual learning media that could be played.

In language development, including introducing English vocabulary to young children, learning media has a big role. This is because media is a learning resource that can help educators provide information and help increase the potential of their students (Khadijah, 2015). Having media in learning will make the process of conveying information easier and help children understand learning. There are various types of learning media, one of which is visual learning media. Visual learning media is the most suitable learning media for early childhood because it relies on the sense of sight, which is to the principles of early childhood learning, namely concrete. There are many examples of visual learning media, one of which is the Busy Book media.

A busy book is an intuitive learning medium made from cloth (especially flannel) or other variations that can be made into a book with an attractive appearance and contains basic game exercises that can train children's movement coordination (Mufliharsi, 2017). The unique thing about this media is that it is handmade, allowing educators to be creative and adapt the media content to children's needs. Therefore, this busy book media is suitable for use as learning media for early childhood.

The statement above is by research conducted by Putri (2022) that the use of busy book media "Math Fun" in developing logical intelligence can introduce numbers to children very well and make students more active, focused, and enthusiastic in the learning process. Using busy book media can also be a strategy for providing progress in the physical aspects of children's fine motor skills in coordinating movements and eyes (Utomo, et al., 2018). Other research by Nurlaela (2018) shows that the use of busy book media with the theme of Transportation Equipment improves children's language development, can increase children's vocabulary, makes children more communicative, and fosters children's interest in the teaching and learning process. Research by Sari (2021) shows that using busy book media with the theme of Plants can improve children's English intelligence. Apart from that, busy book media is also able to stimulate children to recognize letter symbols and sounds, arrange letters into words, and form meaningful sentences (Afrianti and Wirman, 2020). Although busy book media has been widely used and developed in previous research. However, there is still little research that uses busy books as a learning medium in developing children's English vocabulary and on specific themes.

Based on this, researchers were able to channel problem-solving through the development of the visual learning media Busy Book based on the theme of the universe which is expected to support children to develop their English vocabulary and provide assistance to teachers in introducing and learning English. By developing this learning media, it is also hoped

that it can generate enthusiasm and develop children's interest in learning English vocabulary.

Therefore, this research is entitled Development of Busy Book Learning Media Based on the Universe Theme to Develop English Vocabulary for Early Childhood of Kindergarten Group B At TK Amir Hamzah Medan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Early Childhood English Vocabulary

The quality of a child's vocabulary can influence the process of language acquisition and development. If children have a large vocabulary, then the development of the four language skills, such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing will develop optimally (Rafiek and Noortyani, 2007).

Cooper (in Jeti, et al., 2018) explains more clearly how to teach English to children, including (1) Always using English so that children get used to it, (2) Making children understand what we say, (3) Letting them children answer using their mother tongue, (4) Teach children basic vocabulary instead of sentences, (5) The media used must be interesting, (7) Use games that involve children, (8) Use songs, and (9) Use stories

Busy Book Learning Media

In the field of education, media is a learning resource that can support teachers to provide information and be able to develop the potential of their students (Khadijah, 2015). Learning media plays a major role in supporting the learning process. With learning media, teachers can easily convey new information or knowledge to students. The application of learning media to the learning process can facilitate the process of conveying information and help children understand the subject matter. Prawiradilaga, et al. (2016) stated that there are seven specific objectives for using learning media, including (1) Providing varied learning experiences to stimulate students' interest in learning, (2) Bringing up attitudes and skills in the field of technology, (3) Creating a pleasant learning atmosphere, (4) Creating active, efficient and meaningful learning, (5) Providing learning opportunities anywhere and anytime, (6) Growing students' learning motivation, and (7) Making the learning process a necessity.

The learning media used for early childhood education is different from learning media at the advanced level of education. Learning media in PAUD has specifications that need to be considered. According to Lillard (in Nugrahanta, et al., 2016), the characteristics of early childhood media are as follows.

- a) Interesting, media must have an attractive appearance using a combination of soft and bright colors so that children have the desire to use it in learning.
- b) Graded, the media must have a gradation of stimuli in terms of shape and color taking into account age so that there is involvement of the five senses and is provided at various stages

of the child's development.

- c) Auto-correction, the media must have error control to inform children in depth about the implementation of activities carried out without having to be told by teachers, parents/supporters.
- d) Auto-education, media must be created so that children are more independent in learning and developing themselves without the help of others.

According to Hasnida (2015), there are 7 criteria for early childhood media, namely (1) Relevant to the child's condition, (2) Colorful and attractive, (3) Simple and concrete, (4) Exploratory and inviting children's curiosity, (5) Related to children's daily activities, (6) Safe and not harmful to children, and (7) Useful and contains educational value.

Latif, et al. (2013) stated that 3 types of media are usually used in the learning process in Indonesia. The three types of learning media are audio media, visual media, and audio-visual media.

Busy book media is an example of visual learning media. Busy book media is learning media that is packaged like a book with an attractive appearance and contains activities that can be played while training children's movement coordination (Putri, 2022). A busy book is a two-way or more communication learning medium made from fabric (mainly flannel) which is designed to resemble a book with cheerful colors, and contains simple play activities that can stimulate children's physical motoric aspects, for example attaching buttons, matching colors or shapes, and sew. Generally given to children aged 6 months to pre-school (Nurlaela, 2018). Busy books are intuitive learning media made from cloth (especially flannel) or in other variations that can be made to resemble books with an attractive appearance and contain basic activity exercises that can train children's movement coordination (Mufliharsi, 2017). Based on this understanding, it can be concluded that busy book media is a two-way or more intuitive learning media made from cloth (generally flannel) or a variety of other materials packaged like a book with an attractive appearance and containing basic game exercises to train the movement coordination of a child.

Annisa (2016) explains that busy books have various advantages, namely: (1) The convenience provided for teachers in determining learning material by adjusting the content in busy books, (2) Teachers can find out students' abilities because the activities contained in the book automatically explore abilities. each student, (3) Students will carry out/play the activities contained in the busy book without any orders from anyone, (4) The students are curious and tend to spontaneously carry out activities without asking for help from a companion, (5) The media is durable because it is made of fabric so that its durability is maintained. This busy book is also the right medium for introducing simple and varied vocabulary, including

colors, names, animals, numbers, and shapes. Based on this explanation, researchers will develop Busy Book media which contains pictures and names and is equipped with simple play activities.

METHODOLOGY

The type of research used is research and development or what is called Research and Development (R&D). Research and development (R&D) methods are research methods used to design new products, test the effectiveness of existing products, and develop and create new products (Sugiyono, 2020).

The place where this research was conducted was at TK Amir Hamzah Medan as a data collection location for observation, interviews, and practicality tests. TK Amir Hamzah is located in Medan Petisah District, Medan City. The research period takes place from February to August 2023.

The research and development of Busy Book learning media applies the ADDIE development model with five steps, namely (1) Analysis, (2) Design, (3) Development, (4) Implementation, and (5) Evaluation.

The subjects of this research are 2 lecturers who will test the validity of the learning media and 1 TK B class teacher who will test the practicality of the learning media.

Instruments are tools used by researchers to collect research data (Rifa'I, 2019). Instruments are measuring tools that researchers use to observe which can produce quantitative data (Creswell in Sugiyono, 2020). The research instruments that researchers used in this research were observation sheets, interview guidelines, and expert validation questionnaires. The data collection techniques that researchers use are observation, interviews, questionnaires, tests, and documentation.

Qualitative data analysis techniques in this research were produced through needs analysis including the results of observations, interviews, and documentation as well as suggestions by experts provided after testing product validation to assist researchers in evaluating the products being developed. Meanwhile, quantitative data analysis techniques are data that is presented in numerical form. Quantitative data in this research was obtained through product validation tests by material experts, media experts, and practicality tests.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The development of this learning media uses the ADDIE development model which consists of 5 stages, namely: (1) analysis, (2) Design, (3) Development, (4) Implementation, and (5) Evaluation (Evaluation). After carrying out these stages, the following research results were obtained.

Analysis

The first stage carried out is Analysis. The researcher carried out a needs analysis which was carried out through observations and interviews with the Kindergarten B class teacher, Mrs. Rini Wahyundari, so that the

researcher had an initial picture of the continuity of the introduction of English in schools and as a basis for making media. Based on the results of this analysis, it was concluded that the use of English had not been carried out optimally because teachers were still focused on prioritizing lagging learning outcomes during the COVID-19 pandemic. The teacher only uses the habituation method in simple expressions, such as when asking for permission to go to the bathroom, or when singing before entering class.

However, this habituation was not carried out consistently, so the child did not say the expression when necessary, and when the teacher reminded him of the expression the child seemed to be stuttering, and could not even say it. In class learning, the teacher inserts a color guessing activity in English, but this activity is not carried out by the theme being taught. This happens because of the teacher's lack of English language skills and the absence of learning media to introduce English. Mastery of English vocabulary does not experience development because of this. Mrs. Rini also said that Kindergarten B students were very interested in visual learning media that could be played.

Design

In this stage consists of the first thing that is done is collecting material, such as ideas or descriptions of activities that will be included in the busy book learning media. The second step is selecting materials, including selecting the type of main and supporting materials used and presenting the writing. This busy book media is made in a square shape. The basic busy book page is knitted with 8 strands of milk cotton thread with a size (excluding frame) of 20 cm x 20 cm for 10 pages with one color per two pages. The design of the cover and contents of this busy book was carried out in 3 stages, namely: (1) Designing each page of the book manually on paper with a ratio of 1:2 of the actual size, (2) Tracing the design on paper in the Ibis Paint into a digital design, (3) Printing the digital design in actual size.

Development

The third stage of research is development. The design determined in the previous process will be realized into a ready-to-use product. This stage begins with providing tools and materials and creating busy book media. The results can be seen in the table below:

Table 2. Final Results of Busy Book My Universe Media

Page	Vocabulary	The final result
Cover	<i>My Universe</i> and Researcher Identity	

1-2	Sun- Cloud	
3-4	Star-Moon	
5-6	Planets	
7-8	Rainbow-Rain	
9-10	Soil-Wood and Stone	

Next is testing the validity of material and media experts, which aims to determine the suitability of the media being developed. The results of the material expert validation carried out obtained a total score of 3,875 which is included in the very feasible category so that the media developed is very suitable and does not need to be revised. The material expert suggested that the material on rain vocabulary be clarified. The results of the media expert validation carried out the second time obtained a total score of 3.8 which is included in the very feasible category so that the media developed is very suitable and does not need to be revised.

Implementation

The fourth stage is implementation. At this stage, a limited trial was carried out using busy book learning media. The results of the practicality test carried out obtained a total score of 3.7 which is included in the very feasible category so that the media developed is very suitable and does not

need to be revised. The comments added by the teacher were that the media used was good, and the children were very interested and enthusiastic in using the busy book.

Evaluation

After the implementation stage is complete, the next step is the evaluation stage. The implementation stage is the stage that determines whether an evaluation needs to be carried out or not. After conducting limited trials and testing its practicality at the previous stage, changes in children's enthusiasm for the introduction of English vocabulary can be seen. Previously, during observations, children were seen to be less responsive and stuttered when introduced to English vocabulary. After testing the product and carrying out activities on busy book media, children responded more and were able to pronounce English vocabulary better than before. The activities contained in busy book media make children interested and enthusiastic about introducing English vocabulary. It can be concluded that, after carrying out validity tests, limited trials, and practicality tests, busy book media based on the theme of the universe can help develop children's English vocabulary.

DISCUSSION

Development of Universe-Based Busy Book Media to Develop Group B Early Childhood English Vocabulary

This research is an R&D (Research and Development) research using the ADDIE model which consists of 5 stages, namely: (1) Analysis, (2) Design, (3) Development, (4) Implementation (Implementation), and (5) Evaluation. The time required for researchers to develop this learning media is approximately 3 months.

The analysis stage is carried out by conducting a needs analysis. This analysis was carried out through observation and interviews. This technique was implemented so that researchers have an idea of how to introduce English in the classroom and as a basis for creating media. Based on the results of this analysis, it was found that the use of English had not been carried out optimally because teachers were still focused on prioritizing lagging learning outcomes during the COVID-19 pandemic. The teacher only uses the habituation method in simple expressions, such as when asking for permission to go to the bathroom, or when singing before entering class. However, this habituation was not carried out consistently, so the child did not say the expression when necessary, and when the teacher reminded him of the expression the child seemed to be stuttering, and could not even say it. In teaching English vocabulary, repetition and emphasis must be used so that children can remember the vocabulary they have learned (Putri, 2018). In class learning, the teacher inserts a color guessing activity in English, but this activity is not carried out by the theme being taught. This happens because of the teacher's lack of English language

skills and the absence of learning media to introduce English. Anal's mastery of English vocabulary does not experience development because of this. Mrs. Rini also said that Kindergarten B students were very interested in visual learning media that could be played.

At the design stage, researchers designed busy book media according to the theme of the Universe. This media was designed by paying attention to the characteristics of media for early childhood, according to Lillard (in Nugrahanta, et al., 2016), namely interesting, graded, auto-correction, and auto-education. The researcher determines in advance what sub-themes will be included in the busy book, and what vocabulary will be contained in these sub-themes. Then, the researcher looked for references for ideas or descriptions of what activities the students would carry out on each page of the busy book. Then, researchers selected the materials used by paying attention to the quality and long-term effects of the materials. Next, the researchers designed busy book media, including the cover and contents. This design was carried out in three stages, namely manual design, digital design using the Ibis Paint X application, and printing the final design.

The development stage begins by providing the tools and materials that have been designed. Then, using these tools and materials, busy book media was created. This busy book media was created by adapting the material to the needs of students. This is the advantage of busy book media, namely that it allows teachers to load media according to their students' needs (Annisa, 2016). After the busy book has been created, the media needs to be validated by experts. The results of expert validation are very important in the development of this media. This Media Busy Book received one revision from a media expert. If the expert validation results reach the "Very Appropriate" category with information that is very suitable and does not require revision, then it can be used at the implementation stage.

The implementation stage was carried out through a limited trial in the TK B class and a practicality test was carried out by the Kindergarten B class teacher. At this stage the busy book media received a positive response from the students in Kindergarten B class, the students looked very interested and enthusiastic in using it. busy book media. If the results of the practicality test reach the "Very Appropriate" category with information that is very suitable and does not require revision, then the media developed does not need to be evaluated.

The final stage is the evaluation stage, which is the conclusion of whether this media is suitable for use and can develop the early childhood English vocabulary for the Kindergarten B group. This media received the "Very Appropriate" category from the two experts. This media also received the "Very Appropriate" category from the Kindergarten B class teacher after limited trials, so this media can be used as a means of developing the early childhood English vocabulary for the Kindergarten B group.

Feasibility and Practicality of Busy Book Media Based on a Universal Theme

The Busy Book learning media based on the universe theme is suitable to be used as a learning media in schools to help teachers develop early childhood English vocabulary for the Kindergarten B group. This media received a score of 3,875 which is included in the "Very Appropriate" category from material experts. The first stage score from media experts was 2.9 which was included in the "Decent" category and the second stage score was 3.8 which was included in the "Very Decent" category. This busy book media also received a score of 3.7 from the Kindergarten B class teacher which is included in the "Very Decent" category.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS*Conclusions*

R&D research on busy book learning media has been carried out following the research and development process. The resulting conclusions include:

1. The busy book learning media is suitable for use in assisting to develop the English vocabulary of early childhood Kindergarten Group B. This can be proven by the results of the validity test and practicality test which received the "Very Appropriate" category.
2. The busy book learning media based on the theme of the universe has been tested for validity and has been validated with a feasibility score of 3,875 which is included in the "Very Appropriate" category with information that is very suitable without the need for revision.
3. The busy book learning media based on the universe theme has been tested for validity and has been validated with a feasibility score of 2.9 in the first stage which is included in the "Appropriate" category with appropriate information but requires minor revisions. In the second stage, obtain a feasibility score of 3.8 which is included in the "Very Eligible" category with very suitable information without the need for revision.
4. The busy book learning media based on the universe theme has been tested for practicality and has been validated with a feasibility score of 3,875 which is included in the "Very Appropriate" category with the description being very suitable without the need for revision.

Recommendations

Based on the output produced by this research, the researcher provides the following suggestions.

1. For Educators

This busy book learning media based on the theme of the universe can be used by educators as a means of introducing English vocabulary to early childhood Kindergarten B group and can also be used in core learning.

2. For Other Researchers

Future researchers who wish to develop visual learning media in the form of busy books or similar are expected to further update the characteristics of the media they wish to develop, for example making it into another theme or sub-theme.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

For advanced research, we hope to be able to see another researcher be more creative in developing media to develop the English vocabulary of early childhood in kindergarten.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author would like to thank everyone who was involved in writing this article, especially the principal and teachers as well as students at TK B Amir Hamzah Medan who have allowed researchers to carry out research at the school.

REFERENCES

- Afrianti, Y. & Wriaman, A. (2020). Penggunaan media busy book untuk menstimulasi kemampuan membaca anak. *Jurnal Pendidikan Tambusai*, 4 (2), 1156-1163.
- Annisa, M. (2016). Pengaruh pembelajaran menggunakan alat permainan edukatif busy book terhadap kecerdasan visual-spasial anak. Tersedia dari <https://repository.upi.edu/id/eprint/25357>
- Arsyad, A. (2013). *Media pembelajaran*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Belajar Azwar. (2012). *Metode Penelitian*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar
- Danuri dan Maisaroh, S. (Ed). (2019). *Metode penelitian pendidikan*. Yogyakarta: Samudra Biru
- Gumita, D. S. M. (2018). Pengaruh media big book terhadap perkembangan kosakata bahasa Inggris anak usia 5-6 tahun di raudhatul athfal arrusyadah I Kedaton Bandar Lampung. Diakses dari

<http://repository.radenintan.ac.id/4168/1/SKRIPSI%20DIANA%20SANT I.pdf>

Guslinda, dan Kurnia, R. (2018). Media pembelajaran anak usia dini. Jakad Publishing.

Hasnida. (2015). Media pembelajaran kreatif. Jakarta Timur: PT Luxima Metro Media

Izzan, A. dan Mahfuddin, F. M. (2007). How to master english. Jakarta: Kesaint Blanc

Jeti, dkk. (2018). Introduction to english language in early childhood education. Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini, 2 (2), 63-78. <https://doi.org/10.24853/yby.2.2.63-78>

Khadijah. (2015). Media pembelajaran anak usia dini. Medan: Perdana Publishing
Khairani, A. I. (2016). Pendidikan bahasa Inggris untuk anak usia dini. Diakses dari

Digital Repository Universitas Negeri Medan pada situs web universitas
<http://digilib.unimed.ac.id/448/>

Latif, M., dkk. (2013). Orientasi baru pendidikan anak usia dini: Teori dan aplikasi. Jakarta: Kencana Pranamedia Group

Liyana, A. dan Kurniawan, M. (2019). Speaking pyramid sebagai media pembelajaran kosakata bahasa Inggris anak usia 5-6 tahun. Jurnal Obsesi: Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini, 3(1), 225-232. <https://doi.org/10.31004/obsesi.v3i1.178>

Madyawati, L. (2017). Strategi pengembangan bahasa pada anak. Jakarta: PT Kharisma Putra Utama

Mufliharsi, Risa. (2017). Pemanfaatan busy book pada kosakata anak usia dini di PAUD swadaya PKK. Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini, 5 (2),

- 146-155. Diakses dari <https://ejournal.bbg.ac.id/metamorfosa/article/view/185>
- Mulyatiningsih, E. dan Nuryanto, A. (2014). Metode penelitian terapan bidang pendidikan. Bandung: Alfabeta
- Nugrahanta, G.A., Rismiati, C., Anugrahana, A., & Kurniastuti, I. (2016). Pengembangan alat peraga matematika berdasarkan metode montessori papan dakon operasi bilangan bulat untuk siswa SD. *Jurnal Penelitian (Edisi Khusus PGSD)*, 20(2), 103-116). Diakses dari <https://www.ejournal.usd.ac.id>
- Nurlaela, Lela. (2018). Pengembangan media pembelajaran busy book dalam meningkatkan kemampuan bahasa anak usia dini di play group islam bina balita way halim bandar lampung tahun ajaran 2017/2018. Tersedia dari <http://repository.radenintan.ac.id/5720/>
- Nurmaleni. (2021). Pengembangan media pop up book untuk mengenalkan kosakata pada anak usia 5-6 tahun di TK Harapan Ibu Sikaladi Kecamatan Pariangan Kabupaten TanahDatar. Tersedia dari <https://repo.iainbatusangkar.ac.id.xmlui/handle/123456789/21434>
- Otto, Beverly. (2015). *Language development in early childhood (3rd Edition)*. Ohio: Merrill
- Paramita, V. D. (2019). *Jatuh hati pada montessori: Seni mengasuh anak usia dini*. Yogyakarta: PT Bintang Pustaka
- Prawiradilaga, D. S., dkk. (2016). *Mozaik teknologi pendidikan e-learning*. Jakarta: Kencana Pranadamedia Group
- Putri, K. C. A. (2022). Pengembangan media pembelajaran busy book untuk mengembangkan kecerdasan logika-matematika pada anak usia 5-6 Tahun. Tersedia dari <https://repositority.usd.ac.id/42968/>

- Putri, R. I. (2018). Peningkatan penguasaan kosakata bahasa Inggris dengan metode bernyanyi pada kelompok b taman kanak-kanak sholeh sukodono sidoarjo. Tersedia dari <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/160603876.pdf>
- Rafiek, M. dan Noortyani, R. (2007). Pemerolehan kosakata anak usia dini di kota banjarmasin. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar
- Rifa'I, A. A. (2019). Pengantar penelitian pendidikan. Kep. Bangka Belitung: PPs IAIN SAS Babel
- Rusalman, M., Febrini, D., Syafri, F. (2021). Pengembangan media buku kegiatan tema semester satu untuk menstimulasi kemampuan bahasa inggris AUD. Al-Abyadh, 4(2), 101-109. Diakses di <https://ojs.diniyah.ac.id>
- Sari, A. P. A. (2021). Pengembangan media busy book untuk meningkatkan kosakata bahasa inggris anak usia 4-5 tahun dengan metode bercerita.
- Silfana, E. (2018). Meningkatkan kosakata anak usia 4-5 tahun melalui bermain tebak kata. Tersedia dari <https://ecampus-fip.umj.ac.id/umj/AmbilLampiran?ref=13947&jurusan=&jenis=Item&usngId=false&download=false&clazz=ais.database.model.file.LampiranLain&i frame=true>
- Soetjningsih, C. H. (2018). Seri psikologi perkembangan: Perkembangan anak sejak pembuahan sampai dengan kanak-kanak akhir. Depok: Prenadamedia Group
- Sohibun, dan Ade, F. Y. (2017). Pengembangan media pembelajaran berbasis virtual class berbantuan google drive. Jurnal Keguruan dan Ilmu Tarbiyah, 2 (2), 121-129. <https://doi.org/10.24042/tadris.v2i2.2177>
- Sugiyono. (2014). Metode penelitian pendidikan pendekatan kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D. Bandung: Alfabeta.

- Sugiyono. (2020). Metode penelitian & pengembangan: research and development. Bandung: Alfabeta
- Udayanti, Luh Melin. (2021). Penggunaan media visual “poster bergambar” dalam pembelajaran bahasa inggris untuk anak usia dini. *Jurnal Lampung*, 12 (2), 182-191. <https://doi.org/10.47730/jurnallampung.v12i2.262>
- Utomo, I. A., Ramli, M., Furaidah, F. (2018). Penerapan strategi bermain melalui media busy book untuk meningkatkan fisik motorik halus anak usia dini. *Jurnal Pendidikan: Teori, Penelitian dan Pengembangan*, 3 (12), 1594-1598. Diakses di <https://journal.um.ac.id>
- Zubaidah, E. (2017). Draft buku pengembangan bahasa anak usia dini. Yogyakarta: Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta.